

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT & VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF TEZACAFTOR AND IVACAFTOR BY RP HPLC IN SOLID DOSAGE FORMS

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Abstract

The pharmaceutical analysis plays a major role in assuring, identity, safety, efficacy, purity and quality of drug product the need for pharmaceutical analysis is driven largely by regulatory requirements. The main aim of the present study is to develop an accurate, precise, sensitive, selective, reproducible and rapid Analytical method development & validation for the Simultaneous estimation of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor by RP HPLC in solid dosage forms. HPLC are reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Method validation is the process to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. Analytical testing of a pharmaceutical product is necessary to ensure its purity, stability, safety and efficacy. Analytical method validation is an integral part of the quality control system. A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Tezacaftor and Ivacaftorin Tablet dosage form. Retention time of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor were found to be 2.140min and 3.096min. %RSD of the Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor were and found to be 0.1 and 0.4 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 99.88% and 99.22% for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor respectively. Regression equation of Tezacaftor is $y = 13967x + 3517$, and $y = 13443x + 4757.2$ of Ivacaftor. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

Key words: Tezacaftor, Ivacaftorin, Analytical method development & validations

Introduction

The pharmaceutical analysis is as the branch of chemistry it deals with the resolution, separation, identification, determination, isolation and purification of a unknown sample. ^[1] Used to detect and measure the interferences in unknown sample. The sample is a mixture of compounds include solid, liquid, semi solid dosage forms. The quality control of this dosage forms can be done by using the pharmaceutical analysis. ^[2] It was plays a major role in qualitative and quantitative analysis of pharmaceutical products. Analytical chemistry has played a major role in the changes facing the pharmaceutical Industry today. ^[3] Traditionally viewed as a service organization, the analytical department has become a significant parameter in the drug development process. Indeed, the demand for analytical data has become a critical path activity for selection of molecule for full development. ^[4] The pharmaceutical analysis plays a major role in assuring, identity, safety, efficacy, purity and quality of drug product the need for pharmaceutical analysis is driven largely by regulatory requirements. ^[5] The main aim of the present study is to develop an accurate, precise, sensitive, selective, reproducible and rapid Analytical method development & validation for the Simultaneous estimation of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor by RP HPLC in solid dosage forms. HPLC are reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Method validation is the process to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. Analytical testing of a pharmaceutical product is necessary to ensure its purity, stability, safety and efficacy. Analytical method validation is an integral part of the quality control system. ^[6]

Materials and methods^[7]

Materials:

- Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor pure drugs (API), Combination Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor tablets (Symdeko),
- Distilled water, Methanol, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem

Instruments: ^[8]

- Electronics Balance-Denver
- p^H meter -BVK enterprises, India
- Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises
- WATERS HPLC 2695 SYSTEM equipped with quaternary pumps, Photo Diode Array detector and Auto sampler integrated with Empower 2 Software.
- UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz cells integrated with UV win 6 Software was used for measuring absorbances of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor solutions.

Methods:^[9]

Diluent: Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, Methanol and water taken in the ratio of 50:50

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: Accurately weighed 12.5mg of Tezacaftor, 18.75mg of Ivacaftor and transferred to individual 25ml volumetric flasks separately. 3/4 th of diluents was added to both of these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution 1 and 2. (500µg/ml of Tezacaftor and 750µg/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution): 1ml from each stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (50µg/ml Tezacaftor of and 75µg/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of Sample stock solutions: 10 tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, 50ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (1000µg/ml of Tezacaftor and 1500µg/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution): 0.5ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (50µg/ml of Tezacaftor and 75µg/ml of Ivacaftor)^[10]

Preparation 0.01N Potassium dihydrogen phosphate Of Buffer: Accurately weighed 1.36086gm of KH_2PO_4 and transferred into a 1000 mL of Mobile Phase bottle and added 500mL of Milli Q Water and sonicated for a 10 minutes and upto volume make up with water. And filter with 0.45micron filter and mixed well.^[11]

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

600ml of Buffer and 400ml of Methanol was added in a 1000ml of Volumetric flask and degas to sonicated for 10 min.

Validation:^[12]

System suitability parameters:

The system suitability parameters were determined by preparing standard solutions of Tezacaftor (50ppm) and Ivacaftor (75ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined.

The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity: Checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Precision: ^[13]

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: Accurately weighed 12.5 mg of Tezacaftor, 18.75 mg of Ivacaftor and transferred to individual 25 ml volumetric flasks separately. 3/4th of diluents was added to both of these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution 1 and 2. (500 μ g/ml of Tezacaftor and 750 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution): 1ml from each stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (50 μ g/ml Tezacaftor and 75 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of Sample stock solutions: 10 tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, 50ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (1000 μ g/ml of Tezacaftor and 1500 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor) ^[14]

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution): 0.5ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (50 μ g/ml of Tezacaftor and 75 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor)

Linearity: ^[15]

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: Accurately weighed 12.5 mg of Tezacaftor, 18.75 mg of Ivacaftor and transferred to individual 25 ml volumetric flasks separately. 3/4 thof diluents was added to both of these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution 1 and 2. (500 μ g/ml of Tezacaftor and 750 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor)

25% Standard solution: 0.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml.

50% Standard solution: 0.5ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml.

75% Standard solution: 0.75ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml.

100% Standard solution: 1.0ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml.

125% Standard solution: 1.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml.

150% Standard solution: 1.5ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipettede out and made up to 10ml.

Accuracy:

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: 10 tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, 50ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters (1000 μ g/ml of Tezacaftor and 1500 μ g/ml of Ivacaftor)

Preparation of 50% Spiked Solution: 0.5ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 100% Spiked Solution: 1.0ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10 ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 150% Spiked Solution: 1.5ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10 ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Acceptance Criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102^[16]

Robustness: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.7ml/min), Flow plus (0.9ml/min), mobile phase minus, mobile phase plus, temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

Method development: Method development was done by changing various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Trial 1: Chromatographic conditions:**Trial 1:****Chromatographic conditions:**

Mobile phase	:	Water : Methanol (50:50 v/v)
Flow rate	:	1ml/min
Column	:	BDS C8 (4.6 x250mm, 5 μ m)
Detector wave length	:	275.0nm
Column temperature	:	30°C
Injection volume	:	10 μ L
Run time	:	10.0 min
Diluent	:	Water and Methanol in the ratio 50:50 v/v
Results	:	In this trail Tezacaftor peak was eluted Ivacaftor was not

eluted and base line was not good, observed more noise and less tailing and USP plate count so, further trial was carried out.

Optimized method:

Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase : 0.01N KH₂PO₄:Methanol (60:40 v/v)

Flow rate : 0.8ml/min

Column : Discovery C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m)

Detector wave length : 260.0nm

Column temperature : 30°C

Injection volume : 10 μ L

Run time : 6min

Diluent : Water and Methanol in the ratio 50:50 v/v

Results : Both peaks are eluted with good peak shape and all system suitability parameters was within the limit so, this trial was optimized.

Observation: Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor were eluted at 2.140min and 3.069min respectively with good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor was very satisfactory, so this method was optimized and to be validated.

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Table-1: Table showing System suitability parameters

S no	Tezacaftor			Ivacaftor			Resolution	
	Inj	R _t (min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	RT (min)	USP Plate Count		Tailing
1		2.140	3355	1.17	3.069	8186	1.35	6.5
2		2.141	3239	1.16	3.076	8362	1.35	6.5
3		2.142	3496	1.18	3.078	8482	1.30	6.6
4		2.143	3755	1.22	3.079	8599	1.30	6.4
5		2.144	3116	1.14	3.081	8311	1.30	6.5
6		2.141	3544	1.17	3.084	8010	1.32	6.5

Discussion: According to ICH guidelines plate count should be more than 2000, tailing factor should be

less than 2 and resolution must be more than 2. All the system suitable parameters were passed and were within the limits.

Figure-1: Specificity

Discussion: Retention times of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor were 2.140min and 3.096 min respectively. We did not find any interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Linearity:

Table-2: Table showing Linearity table for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor.

Tezacaftor		Ivacaftor	
Conc (µg/mL)	Peak area	Conc (µg/mL)	Peak area
0	0	0	0
12.5	173212	18.75	256200
25	352700	37.5	506118
37.5	537044	56.25	756530
50	706138	75	1045045
62.5	884091	93.75	1256787
75	1037735	112.5	1505843

Discussion: Six linear concentrations of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Tezacaftor was $y = 13967x + 3517$ and of Ivacaftor was $y = 13443x + 4757.2$. Correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 for the two drugs.

Precision:**System Precision:****Table-3: System precision table of Tezacaftor**

Conc. Level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample - 01	50.12	700784	100.36
	Sample - 02	50.13	701693	100.25
	Sample - 03	50.13	700263	100.21
	Sample - 04	50.12	700289	100.38
	Sample - 05	50.14	701012	100.29
	Sample - 06	50.13	700278	100.28
Average:			700720	100.295
SD.:			570.3	0.06
% RSD:			0.1	0.06
Conc. level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MIDDLE LEVEL (100%)	Sample -01	75.01	1077925	99.26
	Sample -02	75.01	1076430	99.69
	Sample -03	75.02	1070669	99.87
	Sample -04	75.03	1075434	99.26
	Sample -05	75.03	1068376	99.69
	Sample -06	75.02	1076531	99.87
Average:			1074228	99.61
SD.:			3799.66	0.28
% RSD:			0.35	0.28

Discussion: From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs. % RSD obtained as 0.1% and 0.06% respectively for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor. As the limit of Precision was less than "2" the system precision was passed in this method.

Repeatability:**Table-4: Repeatability table of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor**

S. No	Area of Tezacaftor	Area of Ivacaftor
1.	701060	1077925
2.	701948	1076430
3.	703844	1070669
4.	700715	1075434
5.	703815	1068376
6.	702194	1076531
Mean	702263	1074228
S.D	1330.8	3799.7
%RSD	0.2	0.4

Intermediate precision:**Table-5: Intermediate precision (Day 1): table of Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor**

S. No	Area of Tezacaftor	Area of Ivacaftor
1.	704596	1042960
2.	708225	1049804
3.	703373	1049846
4.	704385	1035211
5.	709615	1046750
6.	708717	1047755
Mean	706485	1045388
S.D	2663.4	5591.0
%RSD	0.4	0.5

Discussion: Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared, each injection from each working sample solution was given on the next day of the sample preparation and obtained areas were mentioned in the above table. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs and obtained as 0.4% and 0.5% respectively for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method. ^[17]

Accuracy:

Table-6: Table showing Accuracy table of Tezacaftor

% Level	Amount Spiked (µg/mL)	Amount recovered (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	25	25.08	100.31	99.88%
	25	24.92	99.67	
	25	24.92	99.67	
100%	50	50.18	100.36	
	50	50.13	100.25	
	50	50.10	100.21	
150%	75	74.6	99.4	
	75	74.7	99.6	
	75	74.6	99.5	

% Level	Amount Spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	37.5	37.22	99.26	99.22%
	37.5	37.38	99.69	
	37.5	37.45	99.87	
100%	75	73.79	73.79	
	75	74.12	74.12	
	75	74.27	74.27	
150%	150	149.26	99.51	
	150	148.81	99.20	
	150	148.86	99.24	

Discussion: Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as 99.88% and 99.22% for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor respectively.

Robustness:

Table-7: Robustness data for Tezacaftor and Ivacaftor.

S.no	Condition	%RSD of Tezacaftor	%RSD of Ivacaftor
1	Flow rate (-) 0.7ml/min	0.6	0.1
2	Flow rate (+)0.9ml/min	0.3	0.9
3	Mobile phase (-) 55B:45A	0.7	0.3
4	Mobile phase (+) 45B:55A	0.1	0.4
5	Temperature (-) 25°C	0.8	0.3
6	Temperature (+) 35°C	0.2	0.8

Discussion: Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.7ml/min), Flow plus (0.9ml/min), mobile phase minus (55B:45A), mobile phase plus (65B:535A), temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit. [18]

Assay

Figure-2: Assay for Tezacafitor and Ivacaftor

Discussion: Assay was performed with the above formulation. Average % Assay for Tezacafitor and Ivacaftor obtained was 100.05% and 99.82% respectively. [19-20]

Conclusion

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Tezacafitor and Ivacaftorin Tablet dosage form. Retention time of Tezacafitor and Ivacaftor were found to be 2.140min and 3.096min. %RSD of the Tezacafitor and Ivacaftor were and found to be 0.1 and 0.4 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 99.88% and 99.22% for Tezacafitor and Ivacaftor respectively. Regression equation of Tezacafitor is $y = 13967x + 3517$, and $y = 13443x + 4757.2$ of Ivacaftor. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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